

Verification of the Effectiveness of Nano Liquid Fertilizer for Food Barely (*Hordeum vulgare L.*) Production in Bale Highland Oromia, Ethiopia

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Abstract

The excessive and unbalanced use of conventional fertilizers degrades soil, water, and air quality, while reducing nutrient efficiency and raising costs. Nano-fertilizers, with their nanoscale nutrients, offer improved efficiency and environmental advantages over traditional fertilizers. However, no research has been conducted on their potential as alternative fertilizers for food barley production in Oromia, Ethiopia. A field experiment was conducted in Sinana and Goba Districts of Bale Highland during the 2024 main cropping season, locally named the bona season (July to December), with the objective of verifying the effectiveness/efficacy of nano fertilizer for food barley production in Oromia, Ethiopia. The experiment consisted of three treatments, viz., nano liquid (Nito and Ammo) fertilizer, control (without granular and nano fertilizers), and granular fertilizer. The foliar spray of nano liquid fertilizer was carried out on the 15th, 35th, and 50th days of planting using the factory recommendation. The results showed a significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) in yield and yield components of food barley between treatments. The highest grain yield (4796 kg ha^{-1}) was obtained from conventional (granular) fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (3842 kg ha^{-1}), while the lowest (2171 kg ha^{-1}) was recorded in the control. Partial budget analysis showed that conventional fertilizer resulted in the highest net benefit of 290,598 ETB with a favorable marginal rate of return of 423.32%, while nano fertilizer achieved a net benefit of 241,980.73 ETB with an exceptionally high marginal rate of return of 161,188.49%. It can be concluded that conventional (granular) fertilizer and nano-fertilizer significantly improved food barely yield compared to controls, with conventional fertilizer achieving the highest yield. Further research should be recommended on the optimum rate, application times, and viability for food barely production across different agro-ecological zones and evaluate the practicality of nano-fertilizers as a supplement or alternative to conventional fertilizers to enhance efficiency and sustainability.

Keywords: Ammo, conventional fertilizer (DAP and urea), foliar spray, food barely, Nano fertilizer, Nito.

Introduction

Fertilizers have an axial role in enhancing the food production in developing countries especially after the introduction of high yielding and fertilizer responsive crop varieties (Swati *et al.*, 2023). The soil application of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers is not much accepted by scientists, but foliar spray is effective in increasing growth of crops throughout their life period. The unbalanced and indiscriminate use of these chemical fertilizers had a negative impact on soil health, human health and factor production (Spiegel *et al.*, 2020; Jatav *et al.*, 2022 and Poudel *et al.*, 2023). Fertilization management is currently one of the most challenging tasks under the field management.

Despite the fact that mineral fertilizers are necessary for the growth of plants, their prolonged usage poses environmental and health risks, such as surface and groundwater pollution. Foliar application is a method of nourishing plants by spraying liquid fertilizers directly onto their leaves, promoting enhanced absorption in the above-ground parts of the

plant (Marzouk *et al.*, 2019 and Borana *et al.*, 2024). Nitrogen and phosphorus applied by foliar application has greater utilization efficiency than N and P supplied directly to the soil.

Nano urea nitrogen and phosphorus nutrition at optimum recommended dose of fertilizer increased root length and root area resulting better uptake of other nutrients and this efficient absorption and utilization of other minerals might have supported growth of crop plant (Borana *et al.*, 2024). Nano-fertilizers regulate the nutrient release depending on the crop requirement, making them more efficient than normal fertilizers (Liu and Lal, 2015 and Poudel *et al.*, 2023). Nano fertilizers are a new generation of synthetic fertilizers that contain readily available nutrients in the Nano scale. Nano fertilizers are highly preferred due to their efficiency and environmental friendliness compared to conventional chemical fertilizers (Janmohammadi *et al.*, 2016 and Al-Jubouri *et al.*, 2022). Thus, nano fertilizers were produced as a potential solution to reduce fertilizer loss in the environment and increase fertilizer use efficiency for crop production, hence decreasing the recommended dose of traditional fertilizers. Nanotechnology-based fertilizers can be more soluble or more reactive than their conventional counterparts (Rameshaiah and Jpallavi, 2015; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2017; Al-Jubouri *et al.*, 2022 and Swati *et al.*, 2023).

Liquid nano fertilizer which is currently the best alternative to common urea fertilizer. One nano urea liquid particle is 30 nano meters in diameter, with 10,000 time's higher surface area to volume size than normal granular urea chlorophyll (Rawate *et al.*, 2022). Nano fertilizers have emerged as a promising alternative for ensuring high crop yield while remaining environmentally friendly chlorophyll. Foliar application of nano urea liquid at critical crop growth stages of a plant effectively fulfils its nitrogen requirement and leads to higher crop productivity.

The newly created nano fertilizer will reduce chemical fertilizer consumption 80-100 times, saving significant foreign exchange on fertilizer imports (Poudel *et al.*, 2023). This foliar application, is a viable strategy for increasing the availability of nutrients to crops in order to boost output. Adoption of nano fertilizers for revolutionary transformation through nanotechnology, which helps to sustain soil health at the same time ensuring high productivity (Shang *et al.*, 2019 and Borana *et al.*, 2024). Nano fertilizers are recognized for their precise nutrient release and targeted delivery at the nano scale, enhancing plant productivity and mitigating environmental pollution.

Nano fertilizers are required in small quantity which reduces toxic effect caused by the extreme use of conventional fertilizers and have higher use efficiency than conventional fertilizers which reduces losses of nutrients. Nano fertilizers are efficiently absorbed by plant because of its ultra-high absorption feature and high surface to volume ratio (Elemike *et al.*, 2019 and Borana *et al.*, 2024). The nano fertilizers are better than conventional fertilizers as they are ecofriendly, cost effective, maintain soil fertility and plant health. Nanotechnology may facilitate enhanced crop yield in an environmentally sustainable and economically steady manner (Ghidan and Antary 2018, and Eid, *et al.*, 2023).

Even though nano fertilizers have such crop production, economic and environmental benefit yet not evaluated on the effectiveness/efficacy and adopted to our environmental conditions. Therefore, this studied designed with the objective: to verify the effectiveness/efficacy of Nano fertilizer for food barely production and to introduce nano fertilizers as alternative sources of fertilizer for food barely production in the region.

Material and Methods

Description of the study area

The study was conducted in Bale districts of Oromia regional state of Ethiopia. The district are located between 6° 31' 30" N to 7° 25' 40" N and 39° 41' 40" E to 40° 25' 40" E in the southern parts of Oromia Regional State of Ethiopia. The elevation of the area ranges from 1500 to 3500 meter above sea level. The study was conducted in two districts of Bale highland (Goba, and Sinana).

Figure 1. Map of the study area

Climatic condition

The Bale climate condition experience eight (8) months of bimodal rainfall that include a heavy rain (July-October) and a small rain (April-June). Some 600-1000 mm falls annually in the lower altitude areas, and 1000-1400 mm in the higher altitude areas. The wet seasons are comparatively warm and the dry seasons are comparably colder at night and warmer during the day. The lowest recorded temperature on the highest is -15°C and the maximum record was 26°C. The two cropping seasons in Bale Highlands are called the Ganna (March to June) and Bona (July to December) seasons in which the experiment conducted during this bona season.

Figure 2. Monthly rainfall, maximum, and minimum temperature and relative humidity of Sinana District

Figure 3. Sun shine and evapotranspiration of Sinana District

Figure 2. Monthly rainfall, maximum, and minimum temperature and relative humidity of Goba District

Figure 3. Sun shine and evapotranspiration of Goba District

Experimental design and Treatments

The experiment was conducted on farmers' fields during the main cropping season (July-December) at four (4) location in Sinana and Goba District using farmer's replications. The land preparation was conducted using both tractor and oxen plow in accordance with conventional tillage frequency. It conducted on the plot size was 5 m x 5 m (25 m²) using 1 m the spacing between blocks and plots with 20 cm between row and plants. Improved bread food barely Walashe variety was used as test crop at 125 kg ha⁻¹ seeds rate. The treatments consist of factory recommended nano fertilizer (1Lha⁻¹ AMMO + 0.5 Lha⁻¹ NITO), Control (without nano and recommended NP) and Recommended NP (69 N kg ha⁻¹ and 69 P2O5 kg ha⁻¹).

Treatments

T1 = Factory Recommended Nano fertilizer (1Lha⁻¹ AMMO + 0.5 Lha⁻¹ NITO)

T2 = Control (Negative control)

T3 = Recommended NP (Glandular form)

Methods of Applications

Depending on the crop and its nutrient or fertilizer requires, the number of nano fertilizer sprays at 15, 35 and 50 days after germination. Before the spray the nano urea (NITO) bottle was mixed thoroughly and apply in the morning or evening to avoid dew (Table 1). In general, the following table indicated the summarizes the sources, types, times, and doses of nano fertilizer:

Table 1. Fertilizers recommendation dose for food barely production

After Germination	Product	Fertilizers Requirement per		Water Requirement per	
		Hectare (ha)	Plot (25 m ²)	Hectare (ha)	Plot (25 m ²)
15 days	AMMO	123.76 ml	0.3094 ml	123.76 L	309.4 ml
	NITO	61.88 ml	0.16 ml		
35 days	AMMO	371.28 ml	0.93 ml	371.28 L	930 ml
	NITO	371.28 ml	0.93 ml		
50 days	AMMO	495.05 ml	1.24 ml	495.05 L	1240 ml
Total		990.09 ml	2.48 ml	990.09 L	2479.4 ml
		433.16 ml	1.09 ml		

Source of Rate: AGRILABH BEEJ LTD

Data collection

Plant height, number of productive tillers, spike length, and seed per spike were taken from five (5) randomly selected from the net plot at harvest and were averaged to per plant basis. Aboveground dry biomass yield was recorded from the net plot area harvested and weighted then converted into kg ha^{-1} . Thousand kernels weight: It was determined by weighing 1000 kernels sampled from the net plot using a seed counter and sensitive balance. Grain yields was taken by harvesting and threshing the grain yield from total plot area and converted hector basis. Harvest index was calculated as the ratio of grain yield to the above ground dry biomass yield expressed as a percentage.

$$\text{Harvest index} = \frac{(\text{Economic yield}) * 100}{\text{Above ground biomass yield}} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The yield advantage of the fertilized plot compared to the control plot was calculated the following formula:

$$\text{Yield Advantage} = \frac{(\text{Yield from Fertilized Plot} - \text{Yield from Control Plot}) * 100}{\text{Yield from Control Plot}} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Data Analysis

The collected agronomic data were subjected to the procedure of analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GenStat 2015 software program. The comparisons among treatment means were employed by using of Least Significance Difference (LSD) fisher protected at 5% significant level.

Partial budget Analysis

The partial budget analysis was conducted using a partial budget procedure described by CIMMYT (1988). The price of grain yield of food barely, urea, and DAP fertilizers were valued during the study year (2025) at an average open market price at local towns, which were 70 ETB kg^{-1} , 38 ETB kg^{-1} , and 39 ETB kg^{-1} at Sinana and Goba Districts of Bale highland, respectively. The nano fertilizer prices landing at Addis Abeba which is NITO 18 USD (2,286 ETB) and AMMO 33 USD (4,191 ETB) were considered.

Result and Discussion

Responses of food barely production to different fertilizer sources

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed that plant height, number of productive tiller, spike length, seed per spike, biomass yield, TKW while not significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among harvested index between the treatments.

Plant height

The analysis of variance showed a significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) of treatments on plant height (Table 2). The highest plant height (98.40 cm) was recorded with conventional granular fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (90.95 cm), while the lowest (79.45 cm) was in the control. This might be due to optimum nitrogen and phosphorus physiological process of plant as it promotes vegetative growth.

The similar results were also found by (Choudhary *et al* (2018) and Borana *et al* (2024) who reported that nitrogen and phosphors promoting cell division to development, vigorous root system and higher yield. The highest plant height with nano fertilizer may be due to nutrient uptake during foliar application. These findings align with Al-Juthery *et al* (2018), Rawate *et al* (2022), Maheta *et al* (2023), and Swati *et al* (2023). The synergy between conventional and nano fertilizers enhances nutrient absorption at the cellular level, optimizing growth and metabolic functions like photosynthesis, ultimately increasing plant height (Borana *et al.*, 2024).

Number of tiller

The analysis of variance indicated a significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) of treatments on the number of productive tillers (Table 2). The highest number of productive tillers (5.75) was observed with conventional granular fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (4.35), while the control recorded the lowest (2) (Table 2). The synergy between conventional and nano fertilizers boosts nutrient absorption, enhancing growth and photosynthesis (Borana *et al.*, 2024). This increases photosynthate translocation, leading to more reproductive tillers.

Spike length

The ANOVA results revealed a significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) of treatments on food barley spike length (Table 2). The longest spike (9.615 cm) was recorded with conventional granular fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (8.135 cm), while the control had the shortest (5.895 cm) spike length (Table 2). Increased nutrient availability enhances photosynthate translocation, accelerating sink development and resulting in longer spike length (Borana *et al.*, 2024).

Number of seed per spike

The results of the ANOVA showed that the treatments had a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect on the number of seeds per spike (Table 2). Conventional granular fertilizer produced the highest number of seed per spike (65.35) followed by nano fertilizer (56.35), whereas the control produced lowest number of seeds per spike (37.95) (Table 2). Nano fertilizers enhance enzymatic reactions and hormone regulation, reducing ovarian abortion and improving pollination, leading to more seed per spike (Borana *et al.*, 2024).

Biomass yield

The results of the ANOVA showed that the treatments had a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect on the biomass yield (Table 2). The highest biomass yield (15160 kg ha^{-1}) was recorded with conventional granular fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (1254 kg ha^{-1}), while the lowest (8520 kg ha^{-1}) was in the control. The highest biomass yield in nano fertilizer might be due to the foliar application might be due to quick absorption by plant and easiness of translocation, which aided in better rates of photosynthesis and more dry matter accumulation, that give higher biomass yield. The similar results were also found by Chandana *et al* (2021); Rawate *et al* (2022); Maheta *et al* (2023) and Swati *et al* (2023). Nano fertilizer improve nutrient release resulting in a higher photosynthetic rate and ultimately, a higher biomass yield accumulation (Adhikari *et al.*, 2014 and Poudel *et al.*, 2023).

Nano fertilizers enhance phosphorus absorption and slow-release nano DAP boosts chlorophyll synthesis, increasing biomass yield. Studies confirm high biomass like conventional fertilizers (Liu and Lal, 2014; Borana *et al.*, 2024). Nano fertilizers significantly enhance grain yield by improving plant height, spike length, grains per spike, and 1000-grain weight (Ahmadian *et al.*, 2021). This leads to a substantial increase in overall biological yield.

Grain yield

The results of the ANOVA showed that the treatments had a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect on the grain yield (Table 2). The highest grain yield (4796 kg ha^{-1}) was recorded with conventional granular fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (3842 kg ha^{-1}), while the lowest (2171 kg ha^{-1}) was in the control. This might be due to nano fertilizer improves nutrient absorption, resulting in optimal growth of plant parts and improved metabolic processes such as photosynthesis, which results in higher accumulation of photosynthetic and translocation to the plant's economic parts, improving crop growth, development and yield. A similar result was seen on broad bean, where the use of nano-fertilizer provided better nutrient accumulation and increased growth activity due to smart delivery system of the fertilizers (Benzon *et al.*, 2015; El-Azizy *et al.*, 2021 and Poudel *et al.*, 2023). These findings align with previous studies (Aziz *et al.*, 2016; Borana *et al.*, 2024), highlighting the influence of agronomic practices. Foliar nutrient sprays with nano DAP and optimal fertilization significantly enhance yield (Sahu *et al.*, 2022; Borana *et al.*, 2024). Nano fertilizers significantly enhance grain yield by improving plant height, spike length, grains per spike, and 1000-grain weight (Ahmadian *et al.*, 2021). This leads to a substantial increase in overall biological yield. These findings closely align with results reported by Attri *et al* (2022), Borana *et al* (2024), and others, confirming similar trends in yield improvements.

The observed yield advantage indicates a 120.91% increase with conventional granular fertilizer and a 76.97% increase with nano fertilizer compared to the control. This suggests that conventional granular fertilizers provide an immediate and higher nutrient supply, leading to a greater yield increase (120.91%) compared to the control. On the other hand nano fertilizers, although more efficient in nutrient use, release nutrients gradually, resulting in a lower but still significant yield increase (76.97%). The high yield advantage under conventional fertilizers suggests that the crop responds favorably to the readily available macronutrients while nano fertilizers, though effective, rely on slow-release mechanisms, leading to a relatively lower but notable yield increase.

Table 2. Responses of food barely yield and yield components to nano liquid fertilizer foliar application and granular NP fertilizers

Treatment	PH (cm)	NT	SL (cm)	SPS	BM (kg ha^{-1})	Gy (kg ha^{-1})	HI (%)	TKW (g)
LNF	90.95 ^a	4.35 ^b	8.135 ^b	56.35 ^b	12540 ^b	3842 ^b	35.15	35.15 ^b
Control	79.45 ^b	2.00 ^c	5.895 ^c	37.95 ^c	8520 ^c	2171 ^c	27.59	35.02 ^b
RNP	98.40 ^a	5.75 ^a	9.615 ^a	65.35 ^a	15160 ^a	4796 ^a	35.04	42.80 ^a
Mean	89.6	4.03	7.88	53.22	12073	3603	32.6	37.7
LSD (0.05)	7.89	1.062	1.028	4.886	1915.1	571.1	NS	6.40
CV (%)	5.1	15.2	7.5	5.3	9.2	9.2	17.5	9.8

Where, LNF = Liquid nano fertilizer, RNP = recommended nitrogen and phosphors, PH = plant height, NT = number of productive tiller, SL = spike Length, SPS = seed per spike, BM = biomass yield, GY = grain yield, HI = Harvesting index, TKW = thousand kernel weight, NS = non-significant among the treatment

Partial Budget Analysis

Partial budget analysis showed that conventional fertilizer resulted in the highest net benefit of 290,598 ETB with a favorable marginal rate of return of 423.32%, while nano fertilizer achieved a net benefit of 241,980.73 ETB with an exceptionally high marginal rate of return of 161,188.49%.

Table 3. Partial budget analysis for pre verification of nano fertilizer

Treatments	N	P ₂ O ₅	AMMO	NITO	AdGY (kg ha ⁻¹)	TB	TVC	NB	MRR (%)
	kg ha ⁻¹		(L/ha)			ETB ha ⁻¹			
Control	0	0	0	0	1953.9	136773	0	136773	
LNF	0	0	1	0.5	3457.8	242046	65.27	241980.73	161188.49
RNP	150	150	0	0	4316.4	302148	11550	290598	423.32

Where, LNF = Liquid nano fertilizer, RNP = recommended nitrogen and phosphors, AdGY = adjusted grain yield, TB = total benefit, TVC = total variable cost, NB = total net benefit, marginal net return

Conclusion

The verification study evaluating the effectiveness of liquid nano fertilizer against a control (negative control) and conventional granular fertilizer demonstrated a significant influence on food barely yield and its components. The results showed that the highest grain yield (4796 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from conventional granular fertilizer, followed by nano fertilizer (3842 kg ha⁻¹), while the lowest yield (2171 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in the control treatment.

Partial budget analysis showed that conventional fertilizer resulted in the highest net benefit of 290,598 ETB with a favorable marginal rate of return of 423.32%, while nano fertilizer achieved a net benefit of 241,980.73 ETB with an exceptionally high marginal rate of return of 161,188.49%. These findings confirm that both conventional and nano fertilizers enhanced food barely production as compared to the control, with conventional fertilizer demonstrating the greatest yield advantage. Consequently, it can be understood that, in light of the research that has been conducted, nano fertilizer deserves to be officially registered by the agricultural authority as input for barely production and additional for further studied.

Recommendations

On-farm trials across diverse agro-ecological zones are necessary to validate the consistency of the results, the nano fertilizer as a supplement, and its equivalency with conventional fertilizer recommended. Given the promising results observed with nano liquid fertilizer, it is recommended that the product be registered, and further studies be conducted across diverse agro-ecological zones to validate its effectiveness and adaptability under varying environmental and soil conditions. Further research should focus on determining the optimal rates, timing, and method of application to maximize food barely yield and minimize soil nutrient losses.

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